

D6.5

EPIC-WE Impact Guidebook

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to 28/02/2026*

EPIC-WE

Empowered Participation through Ideating
Cultural Worlds and Environments

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Reviewed by	Kim Holflod (AU), Susannah Montgomery (NISV), Rasmus Wiinstedt Tscherning (CBN), Rikke Toft Nørgård (AU)

- 1 PU = Public
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V2		Second Draft (Submitted Version)
V3		Third Draft (after COO and EB revision)
V4		Fourth draft
V5		Final version

Acronyms and Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
CBC	Fonden Creative Business Network
CGJ	Cultural Game Jam
CH	Cultural Hub
CHI	Cultural Heritage Institutions
CI	Creative Industries
CYM	Children, Youth and Media
EPIC-WE	Empowered Participation through Ideating Environments
KEA	KEA European Affairs
LL	Living Lab
NISV	Netherlands Institute for Sound & Vision
QH	Quadruple Helix Ecosystem
YC	Youth Citizens

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Executive Summary

Executive Summary

This deliverable, D6.5 *EPIC-WE Impact Guidebook*, translates the findings of D6.4 - *Impact of Cultural Game Jams* and the strategic insights from the EPIC-WE *Policy Briefs* (D6.1, D6.2 and D6.3) into a short, practical tool for organisations wishing to understand, design, measure, and communicate the impact of Cultural Game Jams (CGJs).

It serves two audiences simultaneously:

Policy and institutional leaders who need

- a high-level overview of impact
- key recommendations
- alignment with EU youth, culture and innovation policy frameworks

Practitioners (CHIs, HEIs, CIs, youth facilitators) who need

- Simple impact design tools
- Context-sensitive qualitative indicators
- Templates to run an impact assessment for their own CGJs
- Practical data collection guidance

The guide summarises the most significant outcomes of WP6 Capacity Building, Impact and Policy, of which the objective was to enable accurate and meaningful impact measurement while providing valuable tools for ongoing engagement with the project's outputs. Moreover, this guide provides a transferable, easy-to-use measurement model for others wishing to adopt the Cultural Game Jam method. Rather than imposing rigid numerical performance metrics, the guide promotes qualitative, narrative-based, and context-sensitive impact assessment. This guidebook should be read alongside the EPIC-WE Policy Brief series — EPIC-WE First Policy Brief (D6.1), EPIC-WE Second Policy Brief (D6.2), and EPIC-WE Third Policy Brief (D6.3) — which together outline the policy rationale, governance frameworks and sustainability pathways for Cultural Game Jams.

Introduction

Introduction

Cultural Game Jams (CGJs) are participatory, co-creative interventions situated within the Quadruple Helix ecosystem (Youth Citizens, Cultural Heritage Institutions, Higher Education Institutions, Creative Industries).

This guide:

1. **Synthesises** impact findings from D6.4 across Aarhus, Hilversum, and Óbidos
2. **Translates** them into transferable guidance
3. **Provides** methodological clarity
4. **Aligns** with EU cultural democracy and youth participation priorities as drawn from the EPIC-WE Policy Briefs.

These rapid overviews are designed to be practical: They help practitioners identify realistic, context-sensitive goals for CGJs and provide policy makers with bite-sized evidence to support decision-making. For more detailed evidence and empirical examples, see *D6.4 - Report on Impact of Game Jams*, *D6.1 - EPIC-WE First Policy Brief*, *D6.2 - EPIC-WE Second Policy Brief*, and *D6.3 - EPIC-WE Third Policy Brief* (policy implications and recommendations).

How To Use This Guide

This guide is designed as a flexible, practical document to support organisations in designing, measuring and communicating the impact of Cultural Game Jams (CGJs). It does not prescribe a fixed evaluation model or a mandatory set of KPIs. Instead, it helps organisations to develop valid, meaningful and context-sensitive indicators that reflect the specific aims, scale, and audiences of their activities.

Readers may use the guide in different ways:

- **Practitioners** (Cultural Heritage Institutions, Higher Education Institutions, Creative Industries) can follow Section 2 step by step to design and run an impact assessment for their own Cultural Game Jams.
- **Policy makers and institutional leaders** can consult Section 1 and Section 4 for concise evidence of impact and policy relevance.
- **Researchers and evaluators** can use the indicator families and narrative approach as a lightweight, qualitative complement to formal evaluation frameworks.

The guide builds directly on the empirical findings of D6.4 (Report on Impact of Cultural Game Jams) and the strategic framing of D6.1, D6.2, and D6.3 (Policy Briefs), translating them into actionable guidance for future CGJs across Europe.

01

Impact Overview per
Stakeholder

1. Impact Overview per Stakeholder

This chapter presents a set of concise impact overviews for each of the four stakeholder groups in the EPIC-WE Quadruple Helix: Youth Citizens (YC), Cultural Heritage Institutions (CHI), Higher Education Institutions (HEI), and Creative Industries (CI).

Each overview summarises:

- the key challenges and needs of the stakeholder group,
- the specific value created through Cultural Game Jams (CGJs),
- the short- and long-term outcomes identified in D6.4, and
- the relevant policy directions highlighted in the EPIC-WE Policy Briefs (D6.1, D6.2, and D6.3).

These overviews serve two purposes:

1. **A reference tool** for practitioners who want to understand what impact they can realistically expect from CGJs depending on the stakeholders they engage.
2. **A synthesis** of the policy and research evidence that underpins the EPIC-WE impact model.¹

The one-pagers also guide readers toward defining their own KPIs. Rather than prescribing a fixed set of indicators, they outline *indicator families* and *example measures* that can be adapted to the specific context, aims, audience and scale of different Cultural Game Jams.

¹ The “Why this matters (Policy angle)” sections summarise how the impacts identified in D6.4 relate to the policy priorities articulated in the EPIC-WE Policy Brief (D6.1). They do not introduce new policy analysis.

1.1 Impact Overview Youth Citizens (YCs)

Challenges & needs

Across the hubs, the following challenges were established for YCs:

- Limited influence in cultural institutions
- Engaged as audiences rather than co-creators
- Lack of experimentation spaces
- Limited influence in heritage interpretation processes

Mechanism

The CGJs repositioned the youth as:

- Narrative designers
- Cultural (heritage) interpreters
- Collaborative creators

Through playful experimentation and cross-disciplinary teamwork, youth could engage actively in game-making and culture-making

Key Impacts

- Increased cultural understanding and agency to interpret cultural heritage
- Strengthened creative confidence, imagination and experimentation
- Development of digital, collaborative and reflective skills
- Greater sense of belonging and inclusion
- Expanded social networks and meaningful peer connections
- Strengthened conditions for empowered participation, agency, and voice.

Why this matters (Policy angle)

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It contributes to EU objectives on youth participation, cultural democracy, digital creativity, and inclusion (D6.1): they strengthen inclusion and empowerment by engaging young people in the game-making process, providing them with opportunities for meaningful and empowered participation. At the same time, they support the development of participatory, youth-centred cultural innovation ecosystems, fostering creative, collaborative, and value-sensitive capacities among youth.

For governance and institutional implications of integrating Cultural Game Jams into long-term heritage strategies, see EPIC-WE Second Policy Brief (D6.2), which outlines structural recommendations for embedding participatory cultural innovation within institutional frameworks.

1.2 Impact Overview: Cultural Heritage Institutions (CHIs)

Challenges and needs

Across the hubs, the following challenges and needs were established for CHIs:

- Engaging youth more meaningfully
- Innovating beyond exhibition-based formats
- Integrating co-creation methodologies

Mechanism

CGJs introduce:

- Playful co-creation possibilities
- Youth-centred interpretation
- Cross-sector collaborations

Key Impacts

- Enhanced engagement with youth audiences through participatory formats
- New approaches for interpreting and presenting cultural heritage
- Increased institutional confidence in playful, co-creative methodologies
- Strengthened ecosystem partnership through cross-sector collaboration with HEIs, CIs, and other cultural sectors

Why this matters (Policy angle)

It contributes to the EU's objectives on cultural participation, audience development and cultural democracy. It also contributes to heritage innovation and digital transformation agendas. And lastly, it strengthens the public value of cultural heritage institutions through co-creation.

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For recommendations on embedding Quadruple Helix collaboration into higher education governance and curriculum structures, see EPIC-WE Second Policy Brief (D6.2), which expands on institutional adaptation and policy alignment.

1.3 Impact Overview: Higher Education Institutions (HEIs)

Challenges and Needs

Across the hubs, the following challenges and needs were established for HEIs:

- Experiential learning integration
- Cross-disciplinary collaboration
- Stronger societal engagement

Mechanisms

CGJs function as:

- Challenge-based learning environments
- Testbeds for applied research
- Interdisciplinary collaboration spaces

Key Impacts

- Experiential, transdisciplinary learning opportunities for students and collaborations beyond higher education
- Increased student engagement, creativity and collaborative skills
- Strengthened partnerships with CHIs and CIs for applied research and education
- Adoption of playful, participatory pedagogies in teaching and learning

Why this matters (Policy angle)

Aligns with EU priorities on innovation, creativity, and skills development. It supports applied, challenge-based and experiential learning models. And it reinforces universities' roles in societal engagement and knowledge exchange.

Broader ecosystem implications for creative industries operating within Quadruple Helix innovation systems are discussed in EPIC-WE Second Policy Brief (D6.2),

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particularly regarding cross-sector value creation and long-term cultural partnerships.

1.4 Impact Overview Creative Industries (CIs)

Challenges and Needs

Across the hubs, the following challenges and needs were established for CIs:

- Early talent engagement
- Responsible innovation practices
- Cross-sector collaboration

Mechanism

CGJs provide:

- Mentorship opportunities
- Heritage-based innovation experimentation
- QH Ecosystem networking opportunities and cross-sector collaboration

Key Impacts

- Early engagement with emerging youth talent and new creative perspectives
- Exploration of culturally grounded and value-sensitive innovation approaches
- Strengthened collaboration with CHIs and HEIs
- Inspiration for new creative processes and partnerships

Why this matters (Policy angle)

Helps creative industries engage early with emerging talent and supports pathways into creative careers. Encourages responsible and culturally informed innovation. Strengthens regional creative ecosystems through cross-sectoral collaboration.

The structural implications of youth inclusion within governance models are further elaborated in EPIC-WE Second Policy Brief (D6.2), which argues for institutionalising Inclusive, Diverse, Empowered, and Youth-Driven Engagement within cultural innovation ecosystems.

02

**How to Conduct Impact
Assessment for Cultural
Game Jams**

2. How to Conduct Impact Assessment for Cultural Game Jams

This section is designed to guide organisers, facilitators, and researchers through the process of understanding and demonstrating the impact of Cultural Game Jams. By following a clear, step-by-step approach, you will learn how to identify meaningful changes, collect relevant evidence, and communicate the outcomes to stakeholders, funders, and participants. Whether you are new to impact assessment or experienced in evaluation, this guide provides practical tools and examples to make your findings understandable and actionable.

STEP 1: Define Your Change Pathway

To begin, it is helpful to clarify the pathway through which your Cultural Game Jam is expected to create change. A practical way to do this is by answering a set of guiding questions. These questions help you articulate who is involved, what resources are used, which activities take place, and what kinds of outcomes you hope to achieve. Completing this exercise will give you a clear roadmap of your event's intended impacts, making it easier to measure and report them later:

1. Who are the relevant stakeholders?
2. What resources are we mobilising?
3. What activities will take place?
4. What outputs do we expect?
5. What outcomes / impacts do we want to enable?

You can use the [Change Pathway model](#) provided by the Europeana Impact Playbook, or a similar model, to map out the expected short-term and long-term impacts of the CGJs (see figure 1).

Figure 1: Example of the Europeana Impact Playbook Change Pathway

STEP 2: Select your Indicators

Choose 3–10 impact indicators depending on your CGJ’s scale. An indicator is a piece of information that helps you understand whether a desired outcome has been achieved. It acts as a signpost: it tells you *if* change has happened, *how* it happened, and *to what extent*. Indicators translate broad outcomes such as “increased creativity” or “stronger collaboration” into something that can be observed, described or measured.

Indicators can be:

- **Qualitative** (subjective, experience-based), such as reflections, stories, or observed behaviours
- **Quantitative** (more objective), such as counts, ratings, or frequencies

Most outcomes benefit from having multiple indicators, so the picture of impact is richer and more reliable.

The Europeana Impact Playbook [highlights](#) that there is no single universal list of indicators. Instead, organisers can:

- Use existing indicator types (e.g., from cultural participation, learning, or creativity research),

- Adapt EPIC-WE indicator families to their own context, or
- Develop new indicators based on the aims of their specific Cultural Game Jam.

The Playbook also encourages the use of Europeana’s [Standardised Question Bank](#), which provides pre-tested, accessible questions that cultural organisations can use to gather meaningful, comparable data. This supports valid, repeatable and user-friendly impact measurement.

Example Indicator Mapping (Illustrative)

The table below provides examples of how broad impact goals can be translated into concrete indicators. These examples are illustrative and should be adapted to the specific context, scale, and objectives of your Cultural Game Jam. The impact indicators should be understood as signals of change, not performance targets. Moreover, combining multiple qualitative indicators provides a richer picture of impact.

Impact Goal	Example Indicator	Data Collection Method
Increased youth confidence	<i>Participants report greater confidence in sharing ideas</i>	<i>Exit questionnaire, reflections, interviews</i>
Strengthened collaboration	<i>Evidence of cross-disciplinary teamwork</i>	<i>Observation notes, facilitator logs</i>
Cultural engagement	<i>Heritage content referenced in game concepts</i>	<i>Game concept analysis, interviews</i>

Empowered participation	<i>Participants feel heard by institutions</i>	<i>Quotes, interviews</i>
Skills development	<i>Self-reported learning of digital or creative skills</i>	<i>Surveys, reflection sessions</i>
Social connection	<i>New relationships formed across groups</i>	<i>Observation notes, testimonials</i>

In this guide, impact indicators are understood as *context-sensitive qualitative indicators of meaningful change*, rather than quantitative, fixed numerical targets. This approach supports validity, relevance and usability for relatively small-scale, creative and participatory interventions, such as the EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jams.

STEP 3: Prepare Your Data Collection

Once you have defined your indicators and prepared your data collection tools, the next step is to gather evidence of change. Evidence can come from a variety of simple, creative methods that capture participants' experiences, behaviors, and outputs. Common approaches include simple qualitative tools, such as:

- Short interviews (3–5 questions)
- Observation notes
- Artefact analysis (games, prototypes, sketches)
- Reflectional conversations
- Post-it mapping or creative journaling
- Quick exit questionnaires
- Feedback sessions

STEP 4: Capture Lived Transformations

Collect and record evidence. Assign roles for data collection (facilitators, participants, volunteers) to ensure coverage of all the various activities. Use digital or physical templates for consistency, such as spreadsheets, forms, set interview questions for each stakeholder group, creative boards, etc. Record both expected and unexpected outcomes, and encourage participants to capture ‘micro-stories’, e.g. short anecdotes and moments about meaningful experiences they had during the game jams.

Guidelines for EPIC-WE Testimonial Interviews

Example questions asked during testimonial interviews:

1. In 30 sec, what is – in your view – the biggest potential or outcome of the Cultural Game Jams?
2. In 30 sec, how can Cultural Game Jams and games through/for culture contribute or add value to the domain of games? Why should we/others do this?
3. In one word, how would you describe your experience with the EPIC-WE project?
4. What is your experience of participating in the EPIC-WE cultural game jam? As an individual and as a group?
5. What skills and competencies did you develop or improve during the cultural game jam?
6. Why should other young people participate in cultural game jams or create games through/for culture? What is, in your view, the value of this?

STEP 5: Analyse and Interpret Data using the Narrative Arc

Look for patterns across qualitative and/or quantitative sources. Map these outcomes against the Change Pathway to see if the intended impacts are being realised. Pay attention to both relational impact, such as co-creation and social aspects, as well as more tangible outputs.

Try following these questions to create a narrative arc out of all the data gathered:

1. **Sensing:** What did we notice?

2. **Recognising:** Which moments stand out?
3. **Analysing:** What meaning do these moments carry?
4. **Reflecting:** What does this tell us about impact?
5. **Sharing:** How do we communicate this story?

STEP 6: Evaluate Against the Indicators

Use the indicators that you set up beforehand as conceptual lenses, not strict bars of measurements, to interpret your results.

For each indicator, ask:

- Where did the impact clearly appear?
- What evidence do we have?
- Which conditions supported or blocked impact?

Summarise your findings in digestible formats, e.g. different chapters per indicator, infographics, or even storyboards or short videos. Highlight examples of impact through quotes and testimonials from stakeholders, which can function as snapshots of their lived experiences. Moreover, use narrative reporting: show the journey of the participants and stakeholders, rather than just stats. And lastly, in case needed, tailor your reports to different audiences: policymakers, practitioners, or participants.

STEP 7: Share an Impact Narrative

Create a story of change that includes:

- Context
- Indicators used
- Evidence gathered
- Highlights
- Quotes

- Reflection on lessons learned for future CGJs: what worked, what didn't, and why?
- Recommendations for future action: encourage a culture of continuous improvement and sharing of best practices.

Minimum Viable Evaluation Design

The table below outlines a minimum viable evaluation design (MVED) for Cultural Game Jams. The table provides an example of a minimum viable evaluation design for each key outcome. Sample sizes, methods, and indicators should be adapted to the specific context and scale of each Cultural Game Jam.

Key Outcome	Evidence Collected	Sample / Scope
Participant Confidence	<i>Short pre/post surveys, reflections</i>	<i>15-30 participants per CGJ</i>
Collaboration / Teamwork	<i>Observation notes, facilitator logs</i>	<i>1 observer per team</i>
Cultural Engagement	<i>Game concept analysis, interviews</i>	<i>10 participants</i>
Skills Development	<i>Self-reported learning surveys</i>	<i>10-15 participants</i>
Social Connection	<i>Exit questionnaires, testimonials</i>	<i>10 participants</i>

03

**Ethical and GDPR
Considerations**

3. Ethical and GDPR Considerations

Since Cultural Game Jams involve (youth) participation, testimonials, interviews, photographs and video documentation, organisers must ensure that data collection and communication practices comply with ethical standards and the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

Key Principles

- Informed consent must be obtained prior to collecting personal data.
- Special care and parental approval must be taken when participants are minors.
- Data should only be collected for clearly defined purposes.
- Participants must know how their data will be used.
- Data storage must be secure and time limited.

Consent and Participation

Organisers should:

- Provide clear, accessible consent forms
- Distinguish between participation consent and media consent
- Offer opt-out options for photographs and videos
- Ensure parental/guardian consent when required

Data Storage and Use

- Store personal data securely
- Avoid unnecessary data collection
- Anonymise quotes where appropriate

Use of Testimonials and Media

When publishing testimonials:

- Clarify whether names will be used
- Allow participants to review quotes if possible
- Avoid publishing identifiable material without explicit consent

Quick Ethical Checklist

Before publishing or reporting, ask yourself:

- Do we have informed consent?
- Are minors appropriately protected?
- Is data securely stored?
- Is personal data anonymised where needed?
- Are participants aware of how their data will be used?
- Have we limited data collection to what is necessary?

04

Policy and Practice Recommendations

4. Policy and Practice Recommendations

For Policymakers

- Recognise CGJs as formats and mechanisms for youth participation and cultural democracy
- Integrate CGJs into cultural innovation agendas and funding schemes
- Support CHIs and HEIs in adopting participatory, playful methodologies
- Strengthen cross-sector innovation through the Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation Ecosystem

For CHIs

- Invite and empower youth as co-creators and partners, not passive audiences
- Use playful experimentation to activate cultural (heritage) collections
- Invest in staff capacity-building around co-creation and facilitation
- Build and maintain long-term relationships with HEIs and CIs

For HEIs

- Embed CGJs in curricula to support interdisciplinary learning
- Use CGJs as testbeds for design research, cultural analysis, and student training
- Strengthen partnerships with CHIs and CIs to support knowledge exchange

For CIs

- Engage with CGJs to meet youth talent early
- Use CGJs to explore value-sensitive, culturally grounded innovation
- Collaborate with CHIs and HEIs for enriched creative pipelines

05

Key Insights from the
Impact Report

5. Key Insights from the Impact Report

This chapter synthesises the most significant findings from *D6.4 - Report on Impact of Game Jams*, translating the detailed impact analysis into a set of overarching insights that explain how, where, and for whom Cultural Game Jams (CGJs) generate value. It summarises how impact emerged across the three cultural hubs in Aarhus, Hilversum and Óbidos, how the Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation Ecosystem shaped transformation, and why the Europeana Impact Playbook offers a suitable framework for measuring this kind of relational, creative and participatory impact. These insights form the foundation upon which the practical guidance of D6.5 is built and are included to help practitioners understand *why* the proposed methods, indicators and narrative approaches worked in practice.

✓ **Cultural Game Jams generate multi-layered, qualitative impact**

CGJs produce change that is emotional, cognitive, social, and creative at the same time. Participants do not simply “learn new skills”; they engage in processes that reshape how they understand cultural heritage, how they collaborate, and how they imagine possible futures. Impact emerges through:

- Playful experimentation
- Collaborative storytelling
- Hands-on game making
- Encounters with cultural heritage
- Moments of confidence-building

Because the method blends creativity, imagination, and reflection, the outcomes are rich, layered and personally meaningful.

✓ **Impact travels through the Quadruple Helix ecosystem**

One of the strongest findings of D6.4 is that impact does not remain isolated within individual participants or institutions; it moves between stakeholders and becomes mutually reinforcing.

For example:

- YCs gain confidence and skills → CHIs see new potentials for youth involvement with cultural heritage → HEIs strengthen partnerships → CIs see new creative potential.
- A change in one helix creates ripples that influence the others in positive ways.

This is why CGJs function not only as learning interventions but also as ecosystem interventions.

✓ **Impact is primarily relational**

D6.4 shows that the deepest changes come from how people relate to each other, rather than from tangible outcomes such as the creation of a game. Impact emerges when...

- ...a youth participant is heard by an institution or creative organisation
- ...a CI professional mentors a beginner
- ...students from different disciplines create something together
- ...heritage becomes a shared conversation rather than a static object

These relational shifts of trust, recognition, equality, and co-creation are what drive long-term cultural and social impact. They cannot be reduced to quantitative KPIs alone.

✓ **The Europeana Impact Playbook**

D6.4 demonstrates that cultural organisations benefit from a narrative, iterative, and experience-based impact assessment that is measured in a qualitative way. The Europeana Playbook fits this perfectly, because it...

- ...prioritises sense-making over metrics
- ...values stories, reflections and personal experiences
- ...is flexible and easy for non-researchers to apply
- ...encourages co-creation and collective interpretation

It helps turn raw experiences into a narrative arc that cultural organisations can actually use.

✓ EPIC-WE's seven indicators act as flexible 'interpretation lenses'

Rather than strict metrics, the indicators developed in WP6 function as *conceptual lenses* that help organisers recognise, name, and communicate impact. They made it easier to detect patterns of change.

EPIC-WE indicators for Impact Assessment

1. Knowledge & Cultural Understanding
2. Skills Development
3. Creativity & Imagination
4. Playfulness & Fun
5. Collaboration & Co-creation
6. Empowered Participation
7. Social Connections

These indicators reflect lived transformation rather than numerical performance, making them suitable for small-scale creative and cultural interventions. Important to remember here is that the used indicators should not be imposed as a fixed template: they are adaptable, scalable, and meant to be customised for different CGJ formats in different contexts. Moreover, the overall insights in this chapter should be read as interpretative guidance that supports impact design and communication, rather than as prescriptive evaluation criteria.

06

Conclusion

6. Conclusion

This guide supports the wider ambition of WP6, which is to enable *any* organisation – whether it is cultural, educational, or creative – to design, measure, and narrate impact in accessible, creative and sustainable ways. It connects institutional policy goals with simple practical methods, making Cultural Game Jams a scalable tool for participation, creativity and cultural transformation across all types of sectors in the whole of Europe.

Although EPIC-WE is a large-scale Design-Based Research project, each of the 12 Cultural Game Jam interventions (CGJs) were individually smaller-scale and stand-alone, typically involving student classes or comparable participant groups. This guide is designed to work effectively at that scale, providing simple, actionable methods for capturing meaningful outcomes.

By combining flexible indicators, qualitative data collection methods and narrative impact communication, the guide offers a scalable approach: methods that are practical for each CGJ, yet transferable across contexts and adaptable for larger creative initiatives. In doing so, it positions Cultural Game Jams as a transferable tool for fostering participation, creativity and cultural transformation across sectors and regions in Europe.

Appendix & References

APPENDIX - TEMPLATE: Quick-start Impact Form

Basic Information

- Organiser(s): ...
- Location / Date: ...
- Participants / Stakeholders: ...
- Theme: ...

Intended Outcomes

Cultural: ...

Creative: ...

Social: ...

Skills: ...

Indicators Selected

- ...
- ...
- ...
- ...
- ...
- ...

Methods Used

E.g. Interviews, Observation, Artefact Review, Reflections

- ...
- ...
- ...

Impact Summary:

- What changed?
- For whom?
- How do we know?

References

Ayaydin, B. (2026). D6.2 Second Policy Brief. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18431979>

Europeana Impact Playbook, V37. CC BY-SA. 2025. <https://europeana.atlassian.net/wiki/spaces/CB/overview?homepagelid=2256699653>

Haselhoff, R., Hazejager, K., & Ayaydin, B. (2026). D6.4 Report on Impact of Game Jams. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18434014>

Wiinstedt Tscherning, R., & Ayaydin, B. (2024). First Policy Brief. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13882418>

<https://epic-we.eu/>

epicweproject@outlook.com

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